

Topic: CIRC BIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's project development assistance (CCRI-PDA)

D5.4 - Promotional Kit

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D5.4 – Promotional Kit

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Abstract	This deliverable contains the promotional material for the DECISO project that is to be disseminated from month 6 onwards (leaflet, roll-up, brochure) as well as templates for promotional material that will be produced and disseminated at further stages of the project (factsheets, infographics); the deliverable also includes guidelines regarding the messaging on the DECISO projects, the visual identity, as well as reference to a picture bank.
Title and number of connected deliverables	D5.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy
Explain Deliverable Dependency/ Connection	D.5.3 DECISO Website
Title of connected external documents	D.5.1 refers to D.5.4 and vice versa
Reference of the document and the link (if available)	Material from D.5.4 will be disseminated via the website (D.5.3) and also printed during events and workshop, reducing the printing activity to the necessary number of copies.

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1. Introduction

This Communication Kit accompanies the Communication and Dissemination Strategy. It includes brief descriptions of communication tools that are provided and can be used by the partners throughout the project life and also after the end of the project for dissemination purpose. This document is accompanied by the actual templates that are made available to all project partners in a folder on the shared drive by month 6.

2. Messaging

When developing the content of different communication activities, it is important to keep in mind the message that shall be sent to the recipient. It is essential to think about some aspects of messaging summarised by the following questions:

What is the objective? What should be conveyed to the recipient? What would we like the recipient to understand or do? What style should the content have? Which key words should it include? How formal should it be?

The table below indicates a suggestion for some of the broad messages that should be conveyed to different target groups (see also Table 3, Communication Matrix, in the Communication Strategy defined within the deliverable “D5.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy – first release”. These messages may not be used verbatim in the actual communications but indicate a direction for the content.

Table 1 Key messages by broad target group

Target group	Key message
Local or regional public administration	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. Let us discuss together how to create a supportive legal and financial framework for CE in the area.
Local or regional politicians	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. This project will benefit your voters – join us to share your ideas on how to best advance it.
National and EU public authorities	Our circular economy solution has a strong potential for stimulating social and economic growth, job creation, and to mitigate climate change in this city/region.
Companies; Industry associations and chambers – as customers	This project will ensure sustainable availability of the resource you need to continue your business.
Companies; Industry associations and chambers – as suppliers/producers	Get on board to create a new product that will help our city/region flourish. Join our working team to seize this opportunity for innovation.
Banks; Credit Institutes	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. Get on board to invest in a project that will help our city/region flourish.
Researchers/CE experts/professionals from sister projects	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. Mutual exchange of learnings and expertise will accelerate the green transition across Europe.
CSOs/NGOs	Promoting this circular economy project/circular economy will help our community become autonomous, resilient to crisis and grow. You are the voie to and from citizens – join us to share your ideas.

Target group	Key message
Citizens	Living in a cleaner environment with access to energy/water/... regardless of global crisis – it is possible. Come and find out about our project and share your ideas.

2.1. Slogan/Tagline

The slogan or tagline of the project is the lead message and should convey the essence of the culture or mood being advanced and implemented. In the case of DECISO, there are several aspects that should be conveyed in the slogan:

Multi-actor synergy – togetherness, participation, action, support, dialogue

Financing – investment, starting a project, realistic plans, risk reduction, reliability

- Investing in saving resources together (FHH, KOYS, OOWV)

2.2. Golden Paragraph

The Golden Paragraph is a short description of the project. It will be used for various communication channels, e.g.: the main page of the website, in press releases, on the LinkedIn account, in emails that the Consortium send out – basically, in any communication activity that introduces the project.

2.2.1. Golden paragraph – short

The Horizon Europe project DEvelopers of Circular SOLutions (DECISO) is supporting support four pilot projects in Hamburg (DE), Alentejo (PT), Northwest Germany (DE) and West Macedonia (EL) to develop financing schemes for circular economy initiatives. Based on learnings from four pilot projects in the sectors water, waste, energy and agrifood, DECISO will then generate financing guidelines for future circular economy initiatives in other regions.

2.2.2. Golden Paragraph – long

High upfront investment costs are a recurring challenge for many circular economy initiatives. Investment is the seed for growing a circular economy. The project ‘DEvelopers of Circular SOLutions’ (DECISO) will support European cities and regions to develop financing schemes for circular economy initiatives. DECISO partners will set up four pilot projects in Hamburg (DE), Alentejo (PT), Northwest Germany (DE) and West Macedonia (EL). The pilots will cover different sectors – waste, water, energy and agrifood. Integrating input from stakeholders along the value chain will allow developing robust business plans and financial schemes. This, in return, shall foster the interest of investors and support by the local community.

DECISO uses an ecosystem approach: it will explore how circular economy business plans can be tailored to different geographical, economic, natural, and social environments. Based on this, DECISO will establish guidelines for financing schemes which other European cities and regions can use for their circular economy initiatives.

DECISO is funded under the Horizon Europe program which promotes research and innovation across the EU. Together with other Horizon Europe projects, DECISO will accelerate the green transition across Europe.

3. Visual identity

3.1. Logo

The logo is the basis of the project’s visual identity. It is a visual reference for the project and enables a quick identification of all DECISO-related materials. The logo is suitable for use on printed/non-printed/website materials and works across a wide range of media. It is available under a variety of shapes so that it adapts perfectly to the support used, such as logo with and without the tagline of the project, as well as a grayscale/black and white version of the logo.

The main versions of the DECISO logo are:

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DEVELOPERS OF CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS

The different formats of the logo are available in the Teams folder WP5 – Task 5.2. – Visual Identity.

Important notice: The DECISO logo must be displayed on all communication and dissemination supports and tools. In addition, dissemination and communication materials must also clearly refer to the European Union emblem (flag). The flag of the European Union, known as the EU emblem, must be displayed on all communication and dissemination supports and tools, as stated in Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement.

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The EU flag can be downloaded [here](#). Further details on the correct use of the EU flag can be found [here](#).

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3.2. Visual identity guidelines

3.2.1. Use of the DECISO logo

A standalone version can be used alongside a group of visual identities of other partners and organisations.

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All partners must respect the following points on the **unapproved use of the logo** – the logo must not be altered in any way, including the following:

- A distortion of the logo
- Changing the colours
- Remove a part of the typography
- Change the order of the colours
- Modification of space between the elements
- A thickening or a net around the logo
- A modification of the typography/fonts.

3.2.2. Graphical chart

The graphical design guidelines can be found in the Teams folder Teams folder WP5 – Task 5.2 – Visual Identity –Guidelines DECISO.pdf.

The **fonts** to be used in line the with the logo are:

DECISO = Raleway Text = Montserrat

Both fonts need to be installed on the partners’ PCs and can be accessed for free on <https://fonts.google.com/>.

In the templates provided in attachment to this document (see section 5), we provide suggestions for the use of these fonts and colours also for titles, texts, tables and other forms.

It is encouraged that all partners use the fonts and colours from the graphical charts also in their own communications to stay in line with DECISO’s visual identity.

Colour codes:

3.2.3. Pilot pictograms

The pictograms for the four pilots are available in different format in the Teams folder WP 5 – Task 5.2. – Visual Identity - Pictos. The same **rules** regarding the **unapproved use** apply as for the logo (see above).

<p>Alentejo</p>	<p>Hamburg</p>	<p>Northwest Germany</p>	<p>West Macedonia</p>
<p>Circular agri-food business models</p>	<p>Strategic framework for financial schemes</p>	<p>Optimise rainwater use</p>	<p>Decarbonisation post-ignite transition</p>

3.3. Partners' logos

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4. Promotion Material

4.1. Overview

The table below provides an overview of the promotion material already produced, and that will be produced throughout the project, as well as the timing.

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type	content	when?	who?
1 Leaflet	Basic info about DECISO	April '23	All: ACR+ Pilot partners to print if needed for local distribution
1 general roll-up	Basic info about DECISO	April '23	All: ACR+
4 pilot brochures	Basic info about pilots	April '23	Layout&structure: ACR+ Text/photo, translation & print: pilot partner
4 pilot roll-ups	Basic info about pilots	April '23	Layout&structure: ACR+ Text/photo & print: pilot partner
4 pilot posters	Specific pitching info for workshop in May	April '23	Layout&structure: ACR+ Text/photo, translation & print: pilot partner
5 newsletters	# 1: Intro to DECISO; Outcomes of EU level Workshop # 2: results of review workshop of financing schemes (in Apr '24) # 3: launch of program, pilot info days, launch calls for projects # 4: outcomes of 2 exploitation workshops (Dec'24 and Apr '25) # 5: Final results of the project (roadmap, planning guide, etc.)	Dec '23 June '24 Dec'24 May '25 Oct '25	Layout&structure: ACR+ Text/photo, translation & print: pilot partner
4 factsheets #1	Market state of the art of CE in pilot areas	Oct '23	Layout&Structure: ACR+ Text/photo, translation & print: pilot partner
4 factsheets #2	Local programs: SWOT, objectives, roles of local actors, competitive elements; composition of working group; PDA implementation models	May '24	Layout&Structure: ACR+ Text/photo, translation & print: pilot partner
4 infographics #1	Financing schemes (risks and legal aspects, risk management)	July '24	Layout&Structure: ACR+ Text, translation & print: pilot partner
1 infographic #2	Business planning guide	Aug '25	Layout, Structure, Text: ACR+ Content: OV/KOYS
1 infographic #3	Cross-sectoral benchmarking	Aug '25	Layout, Structure, Text: ACR+ Content: OV/KOYS

4.2. Leaflet

One general leaflet is created by month 6 of the project. It provides short information on the project – its objectives and key activities; the pilot activities; the partners; and the timeline.

Given the ambition of reducing the project's footprint, the leaflet is primarily be available online, possibly accessible through a QR code. A few prints will be available at workshops and conferences and each organiser will print the necessary number. The leaflet can be found in the Annex to this document.

4.3. Roll-ups

ACR+ created one general roll-up for workshops and conferences with the key information of the project – similar to information contained in the leaflet, but in a more condensed version. Additionally, ACR+ will create a template for a roll-up for each pilot, and pilot partners will adapt the content for those. The roll-up can be found in the Annex to this document.

4.4. Brochure

A brochure for each pilot (4 in total) is created by month 6 of the project. It provides general information about the project envisaged. The pilot partners prepare the information for each of these points in a

template designed by ACR+ and ACR+ reviews and edits, if necessary. Each brochure is available in English and in the national language. The brochure can be found in the Annex to this document.

4.5. Infographic

Infographics will summarise project results at different stages of the project. The following infographics (6 in total) are envisaged (see also Table 6 in the deliverable “D5.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy – first release”):

Table 2 Infographics

No.	Date	Point in project progress	Infographic content
#1 (1 per pilot)	July 2024	Pilots will have developed their local programs and PDAs; financing schemes will have been specified and potential risks identified	The infographic will accompany factsheet #2 and will provide information on the financing schemes including risks and legal aspects
#2 (1 general)	Aug 2025	The consortium will have prepared a business planning guide with different business models	The infographic will show the guide in a snapshot
#3 (1 general)	Aug 2025	The consortium will have conducted a comparative analysis of pilot’s experiences and prepared a model for cross-sectoral benchmarking	The infographic will summarise the insights on cross-sectoral benchmarking

4.6. Factsheets

The Consortium will prepare two factsheets per pilot:

Table 3 Factsheets

No.	Date	Point in project progress	Factsheet content
#1	October 2023	First stakeholder discussions have taken place; market analysis has taken place; a stakeholder working group per pilot is established.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SH Working Group – who is participating • Market analysis – challenges/ barriers, needs and opportunities • Good practices (local, national, EU) relevant for this pilot
#2	May/June 2024	Pilot programs are further specified and additional analysis has been carried out. PDA implementation models are defined.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local programs: SWOT, objectives, roles of local actors, competitive elements • PDA implementation models: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Actions in each pilot ○ Actors involved in PDA ○ Timing, deadlines, milestones ○ Necessary operational services ○ Qualitative and quantitative indicators ○ Monitoring and evaluation strategy

4.7. Posters

In the context of the first workshop organised in Brussels, 4 posters will be created, one for each pilot, indicating the project idea, approaches, and approximate size of the project. The information will be used during the workshop to pitch the project to potential investors but will also raise interest from other project promoters and interested parties about the projects. The project poster can be found in the Annex to this document.

5. Pictures

Some communication material might require adding some pictures to lighten up the page. Some pictures selected by ACR+ can already be found in the [shared folder](#). All partners are invited to add pictures here when they come across them, which might be of use to other partners. Partners will respect the copyright rules applicable for the images they use.

The following image banks provide pictures free of copyrights:

- Pexels (www.pexels.com)
- Unsplash (www.unplash.com)

Even though these platforms do not require it, it is good practice to mention the photographer's name if feasible in the communication tool.

6. Templates

Three templates (general word document, letterhead and power point presentation) have been created and uploaded in the shared Teams folder WP5 – Task 5.2. – Templates. Furthermore, this folder contains some graphic elements that can be used by the consortium when communicating with stakeholders.

7. Annex – Promotion materials

- 1- General Project Leaflet
- 2- General Project Roll-Up
- 3- Pilot brochures
- 4- Pilot Roll-Ups

